

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

UNDERSTANDING FAILURE INITIATION LOCATIONS IN STOCHASTIC VIRTUAL COMPOSITE SPECIMENS USING A MACHINE LEARNING FRAMEWORK

N. Balasubramani, N. Chowdhury, and G. Pearce

School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, UNSW Sydney, Australia

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Multi-level System Design Practice

Hierarchy & Uncertainty

Hierarchy & Uncertainty

Structure observed in real-life

Models generated for finite element analysis

Learning from WWFE

- Consideration of **multi-scale structural information**, temporal and thermal effects during manufacturing and in-service
- Emphasis on **modelling constituent level failure** to understand the fundamental and local material behaviour
- Probabilistic approaches to consider the aforementioned **uncertainties** in loading, material properties, manufacturing processes

Research Statement

To develop a **generally applicable and validated predictive model** for understanding structural failure in textile composite materials with focus on **damage within the constituent phases** by considering the **uncertainties** of the material parameters and geometric features observed at **micro and meso-scales**.

Multiscale Modelling

Run-time computations

Stored as material database

Concurrent Modelling

Hierarchical Modelling

Multiscale Modelling

$${}^m \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = {}^m \mathbf{M} : \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + {}^m \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \quad \Delta T$$

$${}^m \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{M} \times \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

Normal strains

Shear Strains

Multiscale Modelling

BC	RVE strain components in 1,2,3 coordinate system					
	ε_1	ε_2	ε_3	$\varepsilon_4(\varepsilon_{12})$	$\varepsilon_5(\varepsilon_{23})$	$\varepsilon_6(\varepsilon_{31})$
$\bar{\varepsilon}_1$				Negligible	Negligible	Negligible
$\bar{\varepsilon}_2$	Negligible			Negligible		Negligible
$\bar{\varepsilon}_3$	Negligible			Negligible	Negligible	Negligible
$\bar{\varepsilon}_4(\bar{\varepsilon}_{12})$	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible		Negligible	Negligible
$\bar{\varepsilon}_5(\bar{\varepsilon}_{23})$	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible		Negligible
$\bar{\varepsilon}_6(\bar{\varepsilon}_{31})$	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	
ΔT				Negligible	Negligible	Negligible

$${}^m \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = {}^m \mathbf{M} : \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + {}^m \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.194 & 1.934 & -0.1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.067 & -0.133 & 0.845 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.482 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.982 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.347 \end{bmatrix}$$

Multiscale Modelling

Unidirectional lamina

Macro-scale

$${}^{m,\theta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = {}^m \mathbf{M} : {}^\theta \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + {}^m \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

Micro-scale

Multiscale Modelling

Textile lamina

Macro-scale

$${}^n \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = {}^n \mathbf{M} : \bar{\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}} + {}^n \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

Meso-scale

$${}^{m,\theta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = {}^m \mathbf{M} : {}^\theta \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + {}^m \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

$${}^{n,m,\theta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = {}^m \mathbf{M} : {}^\theta \left({}^n \mathbf{M} : \bar{\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}} + {}^n \mathbf{A} \Delta T \right) + {}^m \mathbf{A} \Delta T$$

Micro-scale

Multiscale Modelling

Abaqus UMAT Subroutine

Continuum Level Simulation

Sub-level Simulations

Failure Modelling

$$\varepsilon_{\text{dil}}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \equiv J_1 = \varepsilon_{xx} + \varepsilon_{yy} + \varepsilon_{zz}$$

Macro-scale

Meso-scale

Micro-scale

$$\max \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{dil}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{dil,crit}}} \right) \geq 1$$

Macro-scale

Meso-scale

Micro-scale

Uncertainty Modelling

Periodic Micro-scale RVEs

Uncertainty Modelling

Acknowledgement

ARC Linkage Project LP150100653

UNSW
A U S T R A L I A

Australian Government
Australian Research Council

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

#ICCM22